

ISic1041

I.Sicily inscription 1041

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

Greek theatre, ancient Acrae

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 6475

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140519

1. vacat
2. [— —]ΝΑΕΣΠ [— —]
3. [— —] ΗΤΟΥΤ [— —]
4. vacat
- 5.

Edition: PHI175487

1. [— — —]ΝΑΕΣΠ [— — —]
2. [— — —] ΗΤΟΥΤ [— — —]
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492668

EDCS 39102194

PHI 140519

PHI 175487

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0220 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi. In Bernabó Brea, L. (eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.54 tav.40

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